

**‘NASULATE GARLIC NASYA’ FOR OVULATION INDUCTION IN
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ABSTRACT

Infertility, particularly due to anovulation, can be a challenging experience for individuals or couples trying to conceive. Anovulation can be caused by factors like hormonal imbalances, PCOS, thyroid disorders, stress, excessive exercise, and certain medical conditions. In Ayurveda, achieving Sreyasi Praja involves key components such as Ritu, Kshetra, Ambu, and Beeja, with the ovum (Beeja) being most important. PCOS disrupts the H.P.O. axis, leading to anovulation in 70-73% of affected women. Tridosha plays a role in ovulation, with Vata, Pitta, and Kapha influencing cell division, follicle maturation, and growth. Nasya Karma, an Ayurvedic treatment, stimulates GnRH secretion and promotes ovulation. Remedies like garlic, which said Bijashuddhikara in Ayurveda is rich in allicin, selenium, and vitamins, help regulate FSH levels, improve blood circulation, and support ovulation. **Methods:** In this particular case study, a 30-year-old

female, married since 8 years consulted the Gynaecology OPD due to infertility for the past 4-5 years and abdominal pain for 4-6 months, along with a history of recurrent haemorrhagic cysts. Her menstrual cycles were regular, and ultrasound revealed polycystic ovaries with a 2.8cm x 3.5cm haemorrhagic cyst. She had previously undergone a two-month course of letrozole for ovulation induction at a conventional hospital but was dissatisfied with the results. Seeking alternative options, she turned to our hospital for Ayurvedic treatment for her fertility issues. Specifically, she underwent a therapeutic procedure known as "Nasyakarma"

with "Nasulate Garlic Nasya". **Result:** Within a span of three months, the Ayurvedic treatment she received led to conceive. **Discussion:** The present study emphasizes the crucial contribution of Ayurveda in obtaining positive results in ovulation induction.

KEYWORDS: PCOS, Anovulation, Vandhyatva (Infertility), Garlic, Nasyakarma.

INTRODUCTION

Infertility not only poses a threat to physical health but also significantly affects the psychological and social well-being of couples. Achieving Sreyasi Praja involves the integral components known as Garbha sambhava Samagri, which include Ritu, Kshetra, Ambu, and Beeja. Among these, Beeja is the most essential, often regarded as Antahpushpa, referring to the ovum. Several factors, such as Dushtartava, Aartava Nasha, and Nastartva, can lead to anovulation. One of the main causes of anovulation is Polycystic Ovary Syndrome (PCOS), which disrupts the H.P.O. axis, causing anovulatory menstrual cycles.^[1] Anovulation can be classified as Beeja Dushti. Depending on diagnostic criteria 6% - 10% of reproductive aged women are affected with PCOS among which 70% - 73% females faces anovulation.^[2] Also the ovarian factor contributes to 15-25% of infertility cases and is the second most common cause. Tridosha plays a significant role in the processes involved in ovulation. Vata is responsible for the proliferation and division of cells and the rupture of follicles. Pitta aids in the maturation of the Graafian follicle through its Paka Karma function. Kapha provides nutrition for cell growth. The ovulatory process is influenced by the aggravation of all three Doshas, particularly Vata Dosha.

Nasa is considered a gateway to the Shira (head).^[3] Nasya Karma, the practice of administering medicines such as Kwatha, Swarasa, Kalka, and Sneha through the nasal route, is mentioned in Ayurveda for the treatment of infertility, especially due to Abeejotsarga. Nasya stimulates the olfactory nerves and the limbic system, which in turn activates the hypothalamus, stimulating GnRH neurons. This can help regulate GnRH pulsatile secretion, triggering proper gonadotropin secretion and facilitating ovulation.^[4]

Ayurveda offers various drugs and formulations for treating artavavaha strotodushti, artavkhaya, bijshuddhi, artavshuddhi, vandhyatva, and symptoms of PCOS etc. Garlic is one such remedy. It is considered as a Bijshudhikar in the Rasayanavidhi Adhyaya of Ashtang Sangraha Uttarsthana.^[5]

Known for its polyphenolic and organosulfur properties, garlic has been used as a nutraceutical spice in modern science since ancient times. Garlic is rich in selenium, allicin, vitamin C, vitamin B6, and manganese. Allicin in garlic enhances blood circulation to the sexual organs in both men and women. Additionally, magnesium helps regulate FSH levels, and vitamin B6 is highly beneficial for enhancing ovulation.^[6,7]

So nasya can be appropriate shodhana procedure to deal with the endocrine disorders where Hypothalamus or Pituitary glands are involved. Hence Nasulate Garlic Nasya is considered for the present study.

CASE STUDY

A 30-year-old female patient sought consultation at the and Gynaecology Out patient Department (OPD) due to her inability to achieve pregnancy for the past 4-5 years and frequent pain in abdomen since from last 4-6 months with H/O recurrent haemorrhagic cysts. Her menstrual cycles were regular, and she had provided her ultrasound (USG) report and several blood test results during her visit. Up on examination, she was diagnosed with the presence of multiple small follicles in ovaries i.e Polycystic pattern ovaries with haemorrhagic cyst of size 2.8cm x 3.5cm. Prior to seeking Ayurvedic treatment at our hospital, she had already pursued medical advice from an allopathic (conventional) hospital and had undergone a course of letrozole induction therapy to stimulate ovulation for many times. However, she was dissatisfied with the results of that treatment. Consequently, she turned to our hospital in search of Ayurvedic management for her fertility concerns.

Marital status: Married since 8 years

Menstrual History: Duration of menstrual cycle was of 4 days with regular interval of 28-32 days with hypomenorrhea.

Obstetric History: G₂P₁A₁L₀D₁ G₁: IUD in 8th month in 2018 G₂: Missed abortion in 2020

Family History: No relevant family history

Past surgical history: There was not significant history.

Personal history: Her appetite, sleep, micturition, bowel habit was all normal.

Investigation: CBC, Urine R/M – within Normal Limits.

Thyroid Profile - within Normal Limits Prolactin - Normal within Normal Limits

USG scan - Multiple small follicles in both ovaries i.e Polycystic pattern with haemorrhagic cyst of size 2.8cm x 3.5cm.

HSG – B/L Fallopian tubes patent

Husband semen analysis - within Normal Limits LH - 8.73MIU/ml

FSH - 4.04MIU/ml

Clinical findings

General examinations

Built - Normal

Weight - 56kg

Height - 150cm

Pulse rate - 80/min

B.P. - 120 /80mm of hg

Respiration rate - 20/min Temp. -97.6°F

Physical examination

Ashtavidha Pariksha.

Table 1.

Nadi	Vata pradhan kapha
Shabda	Samyak
Mala	Sama
Sparsha	Sheetal
Mutra	Samyak
Mutra	Pravariti
Drika	Samanya
Jihwa	Sama
Aakriti	Madhyam

Dashvidha Pariksha.

Table 2

Prakriti (nature)	Vatakaphaj
Sara (Purest body tissue)	Madhyama (medium)
Samhanana (Body compact)	Madhyama (medium)
Pramana (Body proportion)	Madhyama (medium)
Satmya (homologation)	Madhyama (medium)
Satva (mental strength)	Madhyama (medium)
Vaya (age)	Yuvati
Vyayamshakti (to carry on physical activities)	Madhyama (least capability)
Abhyavarana Shakti	Madhyama (least capability)
Jarana shakti	Madhyama (least capability)

Systemic Examination

CVS: Heart sounds (S1,S2) : normal

CNS : concious and oriented to time and place.

Respiratory system : normal bilateral air entry, no added sounds. No abnormality found on other system.

Per abdomen

Soft. Non tender and no organomegaly was detected.

Per-vaginal examination

Anteverted freely mobile normal size uterus.

Per-speculum examination

No e/o cervical erosion or Nabothian cysts or any cervical growth

TREATMENT SCHEDULE

The treatment was carried out with Nasya of ‘Nasulate Garlic Nasya’

- 2 drops BD (15 min prior morning meal and Swapnakala) From stoppage of menses upto ovulation or maximum 21 days

RESULT

Within the brief time frame of just three month, the Ayurvedic therapeutic interventions she underwent resulted in successful ovulation and got conceived.

Image 1: Report of 1st cycle Follicular.

ADITI DIAGNOSTIC & RESEARCH CENTRE ASHTA PCPNDT Reg. No. 169
 Multislice CT Scan | Ultrasonography | 3D/4D | Color Doppler
 Echocardiography | EEG | Digital X-ray | Laboratory

Patients Name	:		Age/Sex	:	30 Yrs/F
Ref. By	:	Dhanvantari Hospital	Date	:	11/01/2024
LMP	:	02/12/2023	EDD by LMP	:	09/09/2024
GA by LMP	:	5 wks 5 days	EDD by USG	:	09/09/2024

USG OBSTETRICS

TVS correlation was done.

Uterus: Bulky & gravid.

Evidence of regular, intrauterine gestational sac seen.

Healthy decidual reaction noted. Fetal pole seen.

Cardiac activity appreciated. FHR-120 bpm

Liquor is adequate

Internal os is closed at present scan

No e/o any sub chorionic hematoma at present scan

CRL-9.2 mm, Corresponding to 5 wks 5 days

IMPRESSION :

- Early single live Intrauterine pregnancy of 5 wks 5 days.

All Facilities Under One Roof

पत्ता : गुरुव हॉस्पिटलच्या मागे, आष्टा इस्लामपूर रोड, आष्टा.

☎ 02342-24221

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 Consulting Radiologist

Study.

Image 2: Final result- Patient conceived.

DISCUSSION

Ovulation plays a vital role in a woman's reproductive cycle, and its disruption can significantly affect fertility. Identifying the causes of ovulatory issues is important, as it helps uncover underlying factors that impact conception. Hormonal imbalances, stress, obesity, and medical conditions like PCOS are common disruptors of ovulation. Addressing these issues is crucial for couples struggling to conceive, as it enhances the likelihood of a successful pregnancy. In Ayurveda, the female ovum is referred to as "Streebeeja," and the process of ovulation is known as "Beejotsarga." Ayurvedic treatments, including Nasya, are recommended for addressing anovulation related infertility.

MODE OF ACTION OF NASYA

In the practice of Nasya Karma, the way drugs work can be understood as follows:

The drug enter the vital 'Sringaataka Marma' (a critical point) and from there, they disperse into various channels known as 'Srotasas.' It's noteworthy that Vriddha Vagbhata was the pioneer in explaining how Nasya Karma functions.

The action of Nasya Karma can be described in the following ways^[8]:

- Absorption into General Blood Circulation: The drugs are absorbed and enter the blood stream, distributing throughout the body.
- Direct Infiltration into Brain's Venous Sinuses: Some drugs directly pool into the venous sinuses of the brain through the inferior ophthalmic vein.
- Direct Absorption into Cerebrospinal Fluid: In certain cases, drugs are absorbed directly into the cerebrospinal fluid, which surrounds the brain and spinal cord.

The peripheral olfactory nerves are connected to the limbic system, including the hypothalamus, which plays a vital role in regulating human behaviour and hormone secretion. Stimulating these olfactory nerves can activate specific cells in the hypothalamus and amygdala. During Nasya Karma, it is beneficial to position the head lower and retain the medicine in the nasopharynx to allow for optimal drug absorption. This position provides sufficient time for the drug to be absorbed locally. Substances that are soluble in liquids are more likely to passively absorb through the cell lining membranes. Additionally, applying massage or local heat (fomentation) can further enhance drug absorption.

This entire process is believed to stimulate the Hypothalamus-Pituitary-Ovarian (H-PO) axis, which activates the hypothalamus and triggers the release of GnRH neurons. This can help regulate the pulsatile secretion of GnRH, leading to proper gonadotropin secretion and eventual ovulation. When the HPO axis is dysfunctional, it can prevent the release of mature eggs from the ovaries, resulting in anovulation.

GARLIC

Lasuna have snigdha, ushna, tiksna, katu, picchila, guru gunas hence it act as a shukrajanana, vrushya, balya and swara-varnakara. It also helps in faster healing of bone fracture.^[9]

It is also explained as Bijashuddhikara in Rasayanavidhi adhyaya of Ashtang Sangraha uttarstana.^[10]

In Kashyapa samhita it is stated that, the person who use to consumed Lasuna will not get affected with any pelvic disease and never faces Vandyatva.^[11]

Introduction of Lasuna^[12]

English name	Garlic
Latin name	Allium sativum
Family	Liliaceae
Prayojyanga	Rhizome
Guna	Snigdha, Tikshna, Picchila, Guru
Rasa	Katu
Vipak	Katu
Veerya	Ushna
Paryaya	Lasuna, Rasona, Yavanesta, Ugragandha.
Karma	Kaphaghna, Vatshamak, Raktapittavardhaka, Shukrajanana
Chemical composition	Volatile oil containing Allyl disulphide and Diallyl disulphide, Allin, Allicin, Mucilage, Albumin

In the view of modern Garlic is a polyphenolic and organosulfer enrich nutraceutical spice consumed since ancient times. It is rich in selenium, allicin, vit C, vit B6, and manganese. It also contains considerable amount of calcium, phosphorous, iron, and vit B complex. Selenium, vit C and vit B6 found in garlic eliminate chromosomal defects. Allicin in Garlic boosts the blood flow to the sexual organs in both men and female. Magnesium controls the FHS. Garlic is rich in Vit B6 which aids in ovulation. All together are highly beneficial to enhance ovulation.

NASULATE GARLIC NASYA^[13]

- It is a oil based nasya and was prepared according to the reference of Sharangdhara Samhitha (Madhyam Khanda Chapter 9)
- Main ingredients: Lasuna
- Base oil: Tila taila
- Mixture was heated on low flame till taila siddhi lakshan appears.
- Taila filled in a suitable container without any propellant.

CONCLUSION

Ayurveda offers a potential remedy for anovulatory infertility that has not responded to allopathic treatments like ovulation induction. Ayurvedic approaches aim to rebalance the body's natural rhythms and address underlying issues. While anecdotal successes exist,

substantiating the effectiveness of Ayurvedic methods requires extensive group studies. Further more, therapies like Nasya, which involve the nasal delivery of herbal treatments, are thought to aid in restoring hormonal equilibrium.

SUMMARY

Ayurveda offers a promising approach to treating anovulatory infertility, warranting further research to confirm its effectiveness in conjunction with conventional medical methods.

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